

**M.M. GRYSHKO NATIONAL BOTANICAL GARDEN
NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF UKRAINE**

**INDEX SEMINUM
2019-2020**

**DELECTUS SEMINUM QUAE HORTUS BOTANICUS
NATIONALIS ACADEMIAE SCIENTIARUM UKRAINAE
PRO MUTUA COMMUTATIONE OFFERT**

ANNO 2019

M.M. Gryshko National Botanical Garden is located in the northern part of Ukraine in Kyiv. The entire area is 130 hectares and altitudes vary from 100 to 190 m above sea level. The Botanical Garden lies on the right bank of the river Dnipro. High hills are cut with many valleys and provide suitable conditions for many introduced plants. The climate of Kyiv is temperate continental. Average yearly temperature is +7.4° C. Mean temperatures in Kyiv are +20.5° C for the hottest month (July) and -3.5° C for the coldest month (January). The highest recorded temperature was +39.9° C and the lowest was -32.2° C. The yearly precipitation is about 550-650 mm and average total solar radiation – 97-100 kcal/cm² per year. The collection of plants from all the continents consists of more than 12 000 taxa.

Director: Prof. Dr. Natalia Zaimenko

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Galanthus plicatus M.Bieb. is native to Ukraine (Crimean Mountains and Kholodnyi Yar Forest)

COLLECTIONS, EXPOSITIONS AND CURATORS

- PF-01-07 "Plaine forests of Ukraine" V. V. Melnyk, Head of Natural Flora Department
PF-08 "Steppes of Ukraine" V.V. Grytsenko
PF-09 "Carpathians" O.R. Baranskyi
PF-10 "Crimea" O.F. Levon
PF-11 "Rare plants of Ukrainian flora" M.B. Gaponenko; A.M. Gnatyuk
PF-12 "Caucasus" S.Ya. Didenko
PF-13 "Central Asia" Yu.M. Nehrash
PF-14 "Altai and Western Siberia" O.O. Rak
PF-15 "Far East" N.V. Kushnir
DN-01 "Gymnosperms. Plateau" O.P. Pokkhylchenko
DN-02 "Gymnosperms. Vydubysky dene" O.P. Pokkhylchenko
DN-04 "Beech Grove" I.S. Marynych
DN-07 "Grove of Lime and Maple" I.S. Marynych
DN-08 "Lilac Garden" V.K. Gorb
DN-10 "Magnolia Garden" Ilyenko O.O.
KD-05 "Annual Plants" S.P. Mashkovska
KD-06 "Biennial Plants, Poppies and Callistephus chinensis" G.O. Goray
KD-09 "Bulbous Plants" N.B. Tarasyuk
KD-13 "Rare Perennials" O.P. Pereboychuk
KD-14 "Daylilies and Ornamental Grasses" T.O. Shcherbakova
KF-01 "New Forage and Raw Plants" O.V. Shymanska
KF-02 "Spice Plants" M.O. Haznyuk
KF-03 "Rare Vegetable Plants" O.P. Bondarchuk
KF-04 "Technical Plants" O.L. Andrushchenko
KF-05 "Energetic Plants" D.B. Rakhmetov, Head of Cultural Flora Department
KF-05.1 "Alternative Biofuel Plants" S.O. Rakhmetova
KF-05.2 "Oil Plants" N.G. Druz
KF-05.3 "Sugar Producing Plants" L. M. Polyukhovych
KF-06 "Lawn Grasses" O.V. Shymanska
KF-07 "Nontraditional Fines Herbes" S.M. Kovtun -Vodyanytska
LR-01 "Medicinal Plants" S.O. Chetvernya
PR-07 "Dogwood, Quince, Persimmon, Azimina, Chaenomeles, Cynoxylon" S.V. Klymenko, Head of Accimatization Fruit Plants Department; O.V. Grygorieva; M. Zhurba;
PR-08 "Actinidia, Schisandra, Viburnum, Blackberry, Honeysuckle, Humi, Hawthorn, Cranberry" N.V. Skrypchenko;
TR-02 "Begoniaceae Collection Unit" Ya. V. Byelayeva
TR-05 "Araceae Collection Unit" Zh.M. Yaroslavlska
TR-10 "Amaryllidaceae Collection Unit" A.I. Zhyla

SEEDS COLLECTED FROM THE BOTANICAL GARDEN

ACANTHACEAE

1. *Aphelandra aurantiaca* (Scheidw.) Lindl. – TR-02

ACTINIDIACEAE

2. *Actinidia arguta* (Siebold & Zucc.) Planch. ex Miq. – PR-11; PF-15, Primorsky Krai, Russia, 1949
3. *Actinidia kolomikta* (Rupr. et Maxim.) Maxim. – PR-11
4. *Actinidia purpurea* Rehd. – PR-11

ADOXACEAE

5. *Sambucus nigra* L. – PF-09, Ukrainian Carpathians
6. *Sambucus sibirica* Nakai – PF-14, Altai
7. *Viburnum lanthana* L. – PF-09, Ukrainian Carpathians
8. *Viburnum opulus* L. – PR-11

AMARANTHACEAE

9. *Amaranthus albus* L. – KD-05
10. *Amaranthus caudatus* L. – KD-05
11. *Amaranthus caudatus* 'Rubra' – KD-05
12. *Amaranthus caudatus* 'Viridis' – KD-05
13. *Amaranthus cruentus* L. – KD-05
14. *Amaranthus cruentus* L. 'Hot Bisquits' – KD-05
15. *Amaranthus patulus* Bertrol. 'Oeschberg' – KD-05
16. *Amaranthus tricolor* L. – KD-05
17. *Amaranthus tricolor* L. 'Hopit' – KD-05
18. *Amaranthus blitum* subsp. *oleraceus* (L.) Costea – KD-05
19. *Atriplex hortensis* L. cv. *Gorodnia zhovta*– KF-03, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1974
20. *Atriplex hortensis* L. cv. *Sadova chervona*– KF-03, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1998
21. *Bassia scoparia* (L.) A.J.Scott 'Burning Bush' – KD-05
22. *Beta vulgaris* var. *ciela* Mog. cv. *Zymnii*– KF-03, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1991
23. *Celosia argentea* L. – KD-05
24. *Chenopodium quinoa* Willd. – KF-04, Germany, 2008
25. *Gomphrena globosa* L. – KD-05
26. *Gomphrena globosa* L. 'Rubra' – KD-05
27. *Moricandia arvensis* (L.) DC. – KD-05

AMARYLLIDACEAE

28. *Allium aflatunense* B.Fedtsch. – KD-09
29. *Allium aflatunense* B.Fedtsch. cv. *Purple Sensation* – KD-09
30. *Allium altissimum* Regel. – PF-13, Gissar Range, 1961
31. *Allium caeruleum* Pall. – PF-13, Talgar, 1961
32. *Allium carinatum* ssp. *pulchellum* L.– KF-03, France, 2005
33. *Allium christophii* Trautv. – PF-13, Kopet Dag, 1961
34. *Allium karataviense* Reg. – KD-09
35. *Allium odorum* L. – KD-09
36. *Allium rosenbachianum* Reg. – KD-09
37. *Allium siculum* Ucria – KD-09
38. *Allium schoenoprasum* L. – KD-09; LR-01
39. *Allium textile* A.Nelson & J.F.Macbr. – KF-03, Germany, 2005
40. *Allium tuberosum* L.– KF-03, Germany, 2006
41. *Allium turkestanicum* Negel. – KF-03, Austria, 2006
42. *Galanthus alpinus* Sosnowsky – PF-12
43. *Galanthus angustifolius* Koss – PF-12
44. *Galanthus lagodechianus* Kem.-Nath. – PF-12
45. *Galanthus woronowii* Losinsk. – PF-12
46. *Leucojum vernum* L. – KD-09

ANNONACEAE

47. *Asimina triloba* (L.) Dun. – PR-07

APIACEAE

48. *Ammi visnaga* (L.) Lam. – LR-01
49. *Astrantia colchica* Albov – KD-13
50. *Astrantia major* L. – PF-01; KD-13
51. *Bupleurum aureum* Fisch. ex Hoffm. – LR-01
52. *Carum carvi* L. – KF-02, Ukraine, 1970
53. *Conium maculatum* L. – LR-01
54. *Coriandrum sativum* L. – KF-02, Bulgaria, 1999; KF-05.2, Azerbaijan, 2006
55. *Eryngium planum* L. – LR-01
56. *Falcaria vulgaris* Bernh. – PF-08
57. *Foeniculum vulgare* Mill. – KF-03, Russia, 1986
58. *Foeniculum vulgare* Mill. cv. Moravskyi– KF-02, Brno, Czech Republic, 2000
59. *Heracleum lehmannianum* Bunge – KF-01, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1974
60. *Heracleum ponticum* Mand. – KF-01, Minsk, Belarus, 1974
61. *Heracleum sibircum* L. – LR-01
62. *Pastinaca sativa* L. – KF-03, Czech Republic, 1959; LR-01; KF-02, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1976
63. *Petroselinum crispum* (Mill.) Nym. convar. *foliosum* (Alef) cv. Urozhaina – Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1966
64. *Pimpinella saxifraga* L. – KF-02, Kaunas, Lithuania, 1979
65. *Seseli libanotis* (L.) W.D.J.Koch– LR-01

APOCYNACEAE

66. *Amsonia tabernaemontana* Walter var. *salicifolia* (Pursh) Woodson – KD-13

ARACEAE

67. *Arum korolkowii* Regel – PF-13, Kopet Dag, 1961
68. *Arum rupicola* Boiss. – PF-12

ARALIACEAE

69. *Acanthopanax sessiliflorum* (Rupr. et Maxim.) Seem. – PF-15, Russia, 1950-1955

ASPARAGACEAE

70. *Camassia cusickii* S.Wats. – KD-09
71. *Camassia leichtlinii* (Baker) S.Watson – KD-09
72. *Camassia quamash* (Pursh) Greene – KD-09
73. *Hosta fortunei* (Baker) L.H.Bailey – KD-13
74. *Leopoldia comosa* (L.) Parl. – KD-09
75. *Muscari armeniacum* Leichtlin ex Baker – KD-09
76. *Muscari latifolium* J.Kirk. – KD-09
77. *Ornithogalum nutans* L. – KD-09

BASELLACEAE

78. *Basella alba* L. – KF-03, France, 2006

BERBERIDACEAE

79. *Berberis vulgaris* L. – PR-11

BETULACEAE

80. *Carpinus betulus* L. – PF-01

BORAGINACEAE

81. *Alkanna orientalis* (L.) Boiss.– KF-04, France, 2012
82. *Borago officinalis* L.– KF-03, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2009
83. *Brunnera macrophylla* (Adams) I.M.Johnst. – PF-12
84. *Cynoglossum officinale* L. – LR-01
85. *Lithospermum erythrorhizon* Siebold & Zucc.– KF-04, Germany , 2011
86. *Lithospermum officinale* L.– KF-04, Riga, Latvia, 2012

87. *Phacelia congesta* Hook – KD-05
88. *Symphytum asperum* Lepech. – PF-12
89. *Symphytum asperum* Lepech. cv. NANU-90 – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2008
90. *Symphytum grandiflorum* DC. – PF-12

BRASSICACEAE

91. *Aurinia saxatilis* (L.) Desv 'Compacta' – KD-13
92. *Brassica campestris* f. *biennis* D.C. × *B. rapa* L. cv. Fitopal – KF-05.2, Ukraine, 2007
93. *Brassica campestris* f. *biennis* D.C. cv. Oriana – KF-05.2, Ukraine, 2007
94. *Brassica chinensis* Rupr. – KF-03, Russia, 1986
95. *Brassica juncea* (L.) Czern. – KF-03, Russia, 1986
96. *Brassica napus* f. *annua* D.C. cv. Yantar-H – KF-05.2, Ukraine, 2009
97. *Brassica pecinensis* L. cv. Pak-Chai – KF-03, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2010
98. *Bunias orientalis* L. cv. Olimpiiska – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2008
99. *Bunias orientalis* L. cv. Zolotyinka – KF-01, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1996
100. *Camelina sativa* (L.) Crantz f. *annua* cv. Peremoha – KF-05.2, Ukraine, 2012
101. *Camelina sativa* (L.) Crantz f. *annua*, cv. Yevro-12 – KF-05.2, Ukraine, 2012
102. *Crambe cordifolia* Steven – PF-12
103. *Crambe maritima* L. – PF-10
104. *Crambe tatarica* Sebeók – PF-10
105. *Eruca vesicaria* (L.) Cav. – KF-02, Kyiv, Ukraine, 2011; KF-03, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2010
106. *Gypsophila elegans* M.Bieb. – KD-05
107. *Gypsophila elegans* M.Bieb. 'Parviflora Rosea' – KD-05
108. *Iberis linifolia* L. – KD-05
109. *Iberis pinnata* L. – KD-05
110. *Iberis umbellata* L. – KD-05
111. *Isatis tinctoria* L. – KF-01, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1970; KF-04, Kyiv, Ukraine, 1976
112. *Isatis villarsii* Gaudin – KF-04, Ukraine, 2015
113. *Lepidium sativum* L. – KF-02, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1976; KF-03, Germany, 1950
114. *Lunaria rediviva* L. – PF-01
115. *Neslia paniculata* (L.) Desv. – KF-04, Germany, 2014
116. *Pachyphragma macrophyllum* N.Busch – PF-12
117. *Raphanus sativus* L. var. *oleiformis* Pers. cv. Kyianochka – KF-05.2, Ukraine, 2012

BROMELIACEAE

118. *Aechmea racinae* L.B.Sm.TR – 05
119. *Aechmea comata* (Gaudich.) Baker TR – 05
120. *Billbergia rosea* Beer TR – 05
121. *Billbergia zebrina* (Herb.) Lindl. TR – 05

CAMPANULACEAE

122. *Campanula glomerata* L. – KD-13
123. *Campanula glomerata* L. cv. Alba – KD-13
124. *Campanula marchesettii* Witasek – KD-13
125. *Campanula trachelium* L. – KD-13
126. *Platycodon grandiflorus* (Jacq.) A.DC. – KD-13
127. *Platycodon grandiflorus* (Jacq.) A.DC. cv. Alba – KD-13

CAPRIFOLIACEAE

128. *Cephalaria alpine* (L.) Schrad. ex Roem. & Schult. – KD-13
129. *Cephalaria gigantea* (Ledeb.) Bobrov. – KD-13; PF-12
130. *Lonicera caerulea* subsp. *altaica* (Pall.) Gladkova – PF-14, Altai
131. *Lonicera maackii* (Rupr.) Maxim. – PF-15, Primorsky Krai, Russia, 1949
132. *Lonicera tatarica* L. – PF-13, Dzungarian Alatau, Kazakhstan, 1961; PF-14, Altai

CARYOPHYLLACEAE

133. *Agrostemma brachyloba* (Fenzl) K.Hammer – KD-05
134. *Dianthus caryophyllus* L. – KD-05
135. *Dianthus chinensis* L. 'Covent Garden' – KD-05

136. *Dianthus chinensis* L. 'Parviflora Rosea' – KD-05
137. *Dianthus chinensis* L. 'Schneeconigin' – KD-05
138. *Dianthus seguieri* Vill. – KD-13
139. *Gypsophila paniculata* L. – KD-13
140. *Petrorhagia saxifraga* (L.) Link – KD-13
141. *Silene chalcedonica* (L.) E.H.L.Krause – KD-13
142. *Silene chalcedonica* (L.) E.H.L.Krause 'Alba' – KD-13
143. *Silene coronaria* (Desr.) Clairv. ex Rchb. – KD-13
144. *Silene coronaria* (Desr.) Clairv. ex Rchb. 'Alba' – KD-13
145. *Silene hypanica* Klok. – PF-11
146. *Silene sytnikii* Krytzka, Novosad et Protopopova – PF-11
147. *Silene viscaria* (L.) Jess. – KD-13
148. *Vaccaria hispanica* (Mill) Rauschert – KD-05

CELASTRACEAE

149. *Euonymus maackii* Rupr. – PF-15, Primorsky Krai, Russia, 1954
150. *Euonymus maximowicziana* Prokh. – PF-15, Hualaza, Russia, 1955
151. *Euonymus sachalinensis* (Fr. Schmidt) Maxim. – DN-04
152. *Euonymus velutinus* (E.Mey.) Fisch. & C.A.Mey. – DN-04

CLEOMACEAE

153. *Cleome spinosa* Jack. – KD-05

COLCHICACEAE

154. *Colchicum autumnale* L. – PF-11

COMPOSITAE

155. *Achillea ageratum* L. – KF-02, Germany, 2003
156. *Achillea collina* (Becker ex Rchb. f.) Heimerl – KF-02, Brno, Czech Republic, 2012
157. *Achillea filipendulina* Lam. – KF-02, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1986
158. *Achillea millefolium* L. cv. Rosea – KF-02, Italy, 2005
159. *Achillea nobilis* L. – KF-02, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1976
160. *Achillea ptarmica* L. – KF-02, Belgium, 1999
161. *Achillea setacea* Waldst. et Kit. – KF-07, Ukraine, 2014
162. *Ageratum conyzoides* (L.) L. – KD-05
163. *Ageratum houstonianum* Mill. 'Albus nanus' – KD-05
164. *Ageratum houstonianum* Mill. 'Rosea nana' – KD-05
165. *Ageratum houstonianum* Mill. 'Rozovyi Schar' – KD-05
166. *Ageratum houstonianum* Mill. 'Tetra' – KD-05
167. *Ageratum houstonianum* Mill. 'Altus mix' – KD-05
168. *Anacyclus radiatus* Lois. – KD-05
169. *Anthemis tinctoria* L. – KF-04, Denmark, 2011
170. *Arcticum lappa* L. – KF-03, Kaunas, Lithuania, 1998
171. *Artemisia abrotanum* L. – KF-02, Ukraine, 2005
172. *Artemisia dracunculus* L. cv. Sybiriak – KF-02, Russia, 2007
173. *Bidens ferulifolia* (Jacq.) Sweet – KF-07, France, 2015
174. *Calendula arvensis* M.Bieb. – KD-05
175. *Calendula officinalis* L. – LR-01; KD-05
176. *Calendula* 'Gaicha Girl' – KD-05
177. *Calendula* 'Пятнашка' ('Piatnashka') – KD-05
178. *Calendula suffruticosa* var. *marocanna* (Ball) Maire – KD-05
179. *Carthamus lanatus* L. – KF-04, Germany, 2011
180. *Carthamus tinctorius* L. – KF-05.2, Czech Republic, 2004
181. *Carthamus tinctorius* L. cv. Soniachnyi – KF-04, Kherson, Ukraine, 2012
182. *Centaurea behen* L. – KF-04, Iran, 2014
183. *Cephalophora aromatica* Schrad. – KF-02, Moldova, 1972
184. *Chrysanthemum coronarium* L. – KF-03, Russia, 1986
185. *Chrysanthemum coronarium* L. 'Colorata' – KD-05
186. *Chrysanthemum frutescens* L. – KD-05

187. *Cichorium intybus* L. – LR-01; KF-02, Germany , 2005
188. *Coreopsis grandiflora* Hoog ex Sweet – KF-02, Crimea, Ukraine, 1975
189. *Coreopsis tinctoria* Nutt. – KD-05; KF-04, Kyiv, Ukraine, 2005
190. *Cosmos sulphureus* Cav. – KD-05; KF-04, Uzhhorod, Ukraine, 2011
191. *Cosmos sulphureus* 'Diabobo' – KD-05
192. *Cosmos sulphureus* 'Flora Pleno' – KD-05
193. *Cosmos sulphureus* 'Klondike' – KD-05
194. *Cosmos sulphureus* 'Origin Chone' – KD-05
195. *Cosmos sulphureus* 'Sunny Red' – KD-05
196. *Dahlia pinnata* Cav. 'Mign Red' – KD-05
197. *Dahlia pinnata* Cav. 'Vesiolyye Riebiata' – KD-05
198. *Dahlia pinnata* Cav. 'Nana' – KD-05
199. *Dimorphotheca sinuata* DC. 'Afrikan Mun' – KD-05
200. *Dimorphotheca sinuata* DC. 'Goliaf' – KD-05
201. *Echinacea purpurea* (L.) Moench – KF-01, Moskow, Russia, 2004; LR-01
202. *Echinops ritro* L. – KD-13
203. *Echinops sphaerocephalus* L. – KF-01, Switzerland, 2004
204. *Gaillardia pulchella* Foug. – KD-05
205. *Galatella sedifolia* subsp. *dracunculoides* (Lam.) Greuter – PF-08
206. *Gazania splendens* hort. – KD-05
207. *Grindelia squarrosa* (Pursh) Dunal – KF-02, Crimea, Ukraine, 1976
208. *Helianthus annuus* L. 'Kleinbluting' – KD-05
209. *Helianthus debilis* Nutt. – KD-05
210. *Helianthus salicifolius* A.Dietr.– KF-04, Donetsk, Ukraine, 2000
211. *Helianthus tuberosus* L. × *Helianthus annuus* L. cv. s. Bahatorichnyi – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 1995
212. *Helianthus tuberosus* L. cv. Fiolet kyivskyyi – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2000
213. *Heliopsis helianthoides* (L.) Sweet. ssp. *scabra* (Dunal) Fernald – KD-13
214. *Inula helenium* L. – KD-13; KF-01, Bulgaria, 1988
215. *Lactuca sativa* L. var. *romana* Lam. cv. Sovskii – KF-03, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1991
216. *Liatris spicata* (L.) Willd. – KD-13
217. *Ligularia dentata* (A.Gray) Hara – KD-13
218. *Ligularia wilsoniana* (Hemsl.) Greenm. – KD-13
219. *Onopordum acanthium* L. – LR-01
220. *Pyrethrum majus* (Desf.) Tzvelev – KF-02, Kaunas, Lithuania, 1979
221. *Ratibida pinnata* (Vent.) Barnhart – KD-13
222. *Rudbeckia laciniata* L. – KD-13
223. *Sanvitalia procumbens* Lam. – KD-05
224. *Serratula coronata* L. – KF-01, Ukraine, 1989
225. *Silphium integrifolium* Michx. cv. Yuvileinyi-90 – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2008
226. *Silphium perfoliatum* L. – KF-01, Ukraine, 1969
227. *Silphium perfoliatum* L. cv. Bohatyr – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2008
228. *Silphium perfoliatum* L. cv. Peremozhets – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2008
229. *Silphium scaberrimum* Ell. – KF-01, Hungary, 1993; KF-05.1, Germany, 1993
230. *Silybum eburneum* Coss. & Durieu – KD-05
231. *Silybum marianum* (L.) Gaerth. – KF-01, Germany , 2006; KF-05.2, Ukraine, 2012
232. *Solidago canadensis* L. – PF-08
233. *Symphotrichum laeve* (L.) Á.Löve & D.Löve – KD-13
234. *Tagetes erecta* L. 'Gold Dollar' – KD-05
235. *Tagetes patula* L. 'Limonnyi Prints' – KD-05
236. *Tagetes patula* L. 'Petit Yellow' – KD-05
237. *Tagetes tenuifolia* Cav. – KD-05
238. *Tanacetum balsamita* L. – KF-02, Crimea, Ukraine, 1975
239. *Tanacetum balsamitoides* Sch.Bip. – LR-01
240. *Tanacetum cinerariifolium* (Trevir.) Sch. Bip – KF-02, Germany, 2007; LR-01
241. *Tanacetum vulgare* L. – LR-01
242. *Telekia speciosa* (Schreb.) Baumg. – PF-09, Ukrainian Carpathians
243. *Tithonia rotundifolia* (Mill.) S.F.Blake – KD-05
244. *Tridax trilobata* (Cav.) Hemsl. – KF-07, France, 2015
245. *Zinnia elegans* Jacq. 'Volchebnaia Rosa' – KD-05

246. *Zinnia angustifolia* Kunth – KD-05

CONVOLVULACEAE

- 247. *Convolvulus tricolor* L. – KD-05
- 248. *Ipomoea hederifolia* L. – KD-05
- 249. *Ipomoea indica* (Burm.) Merrill. – KD-05
- 250. *Ipomoea magnusiana* Schinz – KD-05
- 251. *Ipomoea nil* (L.) Roth – KD-05
- 252. *Ipomoea purpurea* (L.) Roth – KD-05
- 253. *Ipomoea purpurea* (L.) Roth. 'Morling Glory' – KD-05
- 254. *Ipomoea tricolor* Cav. – KD-05
- 255. *Ipomoea tricolor* 'Feringa' – KD-05
- 256. *Ipomoea tricolor* 'Heverli Blue' – KD-05
- 257. *Ipomoea tricolor* 'Miky Wey' – KD-05
- 258. *Ipomoea tricolor* 'Scarlet' – KD-05
- 259. *Ipomoea tricolor* 'Scarlet O'Hara' – KD-05

CORNACEAE

- 260. *Cornus cousa* Nakai. – PR-07
- 261. *Cornus florida* (L.) Rafin. ex Jacks – PR-07
- 262. *Cornus mas* L. – PR-07
- 263. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Alesha – PR-07
- 264. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Bukovinskiy – PR-07
- 265. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Ekzoticheskii – PR-07
- 266. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Elegantnyi – PR-07
- 267. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Grenader – PR-07
- 268. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Korolovyi – PR-07
- 269. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Korolovyi Marka – PR-07
- 270. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Kostia – PR-07
- 271. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Lukianovskiy – PR-07
- 272. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Nehznyi – PR-07
- 273. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Nikolka – PR-07
- 274. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Pervenets – PR-07
- 275. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Priorskiy – PR-07
- 276. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Radost – PR-07
- 277. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Semen – PR-07
- 278. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Starokievskiy – PR-07
- 279. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Svetliachok – PR-07
- 280. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Vavilovets – PR-07
- 281. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Vladimirskiy – PR-07
- 282. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Vydubetskiy – PR-07
- 283. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Vyshgorodskiy – PR-07
- 284. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Yantarnyi – PR-07
- 285. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Yelena – PR-07
- 286. *Cornus mas* L. cv. Yevgeniya – PR-07
- 287. *Cornus officinalis* Sieb. et Zucc. – PR-07

CRASSULACEAE

- 288. *Rhodiola linearifolia* (Royle) Fu – KF-02, Kyiv, Ukraine, 1998
- 289. *Sedum aizoon* L. – KD-13

CUCURBITACEAE

- 290. *Cucumis metuliferus* E.Mey. ex Naudin. – KF-03, France, 2010
- 291. *Cyclanthera pedata* Shrad. – KF-03, Moldova, 2003
- 292. *Momordica balsamina* L. – KF-03, Germany, 2009
- 293. *Momordica charantia* L. – KF-03, Japan, 2009

CUPRESSACEAE

- 294. *Chamaecyparis lawsoniana* (A. Murray bis) Parl. – DN-01, Arboretum Wageningen, Netherlands, 1948
- 295. *Juniperus communis* L. – PF-14, Altai
- 296. *Juniperus sabina* L. – PF-13, Trans-Ili Alatau, Kazakhstan, 1961
- 297. *Juniperus scopulorum* Sarg. – DN-01, Dacota, USA, 1949
- 298. *Juniperus virginiana* L. – DN-01, Germany; 1947, Nebraska, USA, 1949
- 299. *Metasequoia glyptostroboides* Hu et Cheng. – DN-02
- 300. *Platycladus orientalis* (L.) Franco – DN-01
- 301. *Thuja occidentalis* L. – DN-01, Germany, 1947
- 302. *Thuja plicata* D.Don. – DN-01, Trostyanets, 1952, 1954

CYPERACEAE

- 303. *Cyperus esculentus* L. cv. Faraon – KF-03, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2009
- 304. *Cyperus esculentus* L. cv. s. Faraon-FKO – KF-05.2, Ukraine, 2004

DATISCAEAE

- 305. *Datisca cannabina* L. – KF-04, France, 2012

DIOSCOREACEAE

- 306. *Dioscorea caucasica* Lipsky – PF-12

EBENACEAE

- 307. *Diospyros virginiana* L. – PR-07
- 308. *Diospyros virginiana* L. cv. Darunok doli – PR-07
- 309. *Diospyros virginiana* L. cv. Darunok mami – PR-07
- 310. *Diospyros virginiana* L. cv. Zobor – PR-07

EUPHORBIACEAE

- 311. *Euphorbia lathyris* L. – KF-04, Ukraine, 2005
- 312. *Ricinus communis* L. – KD-05
- 313. *Ricinus communis* L. 'Gibsonii Impala' – KD-05

FAGACEAE

- 314. *Fagus sylvatica* L. – PF-09, Ukrainian Carpathians

GENTIANACEAE

- 315. *Gentiana dahurica* Fisch. – KD-13
- 316. *Gentiana dahurica* Fisch. cv. Nikita – KD-13
- 317. *Gentiana tibetica* King ex Hook. – KD-13

GERANIACEAE

- 318. *Geranium phaeum* L. – PF-09, Ukrainian Carpathians

GINKGOACEAE

- 319. *Ginkgo biloba* L. – DN-01, Bucharest, 1957

IRIDACEAE

- 320. *Crocus angustifolius* West. – PF-11
- 321. *Crocus speciosus* M.Bieb. – PF-11
- 322. *Iris domestica* (L.) Goldblatt & Mabb. – KD-13
- 323. *Iris pseudacorus* Schur – PF-11
- 324. *Iris sibirica* L. – PF-11

LAMIACEAE

- 325. *Agastache foeniculum* (Pursh) Kuntze cv. Golden Jubilee – KD-13
- 326. *Agastache foeniculum* (Pursh) Kuntze, cv. Leleka – KF-02, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1997
- 327. *Agastache foeniculum* (Pursh) Kuntze, cv. Synii veleten – KF-02, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1999
- 328. *Agastache mexicana* (Kunth) Lint et Epling – KF-07, Russia, 2014

329. *Agastache rugosa* (Fisch. & C. A. Mey.) Kuntze – KF-07, Japan, 2018
330. *Agastache rugosa* (Fisch. & C.A.Mey.) Kuntze cv. Alabaster– KF-02, Poland, 2015
331. *Agastache scrofularifolia* (Willd.) Kuntze – KF-07, Germany , 2014
332. *Agastache urticifolia* (Benth.) Kuntze cv. Weibe Kerze – KF-07, Germany , 2013
333. *Clinopodium multicaule* (Maxim.) Kuntze– KF-02, France, 2017
334. *Clinopodium nepeta* (L.) Kuntze – KF-02, Lisboa, Portugal, 1964
335. *Datura innoxia* Mill. – KD-05
336. *Datura metel* L. – KD-05
337. *Datura metel* var. *inermis* (Juss.) Hupka – KD-05
338. *Dracocephalum moldavica* L. – KF-02, Russia, 1976
339. *Dracocephalum moldavica* L. cv. Perlynka– KF-02, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2001
340. *Elsholtzia ciliata* (Thunb.) Hyl. – KF-02, Ukraine, 2005
341. *Elsholtzia stauntonii* Benth.– KF-02, Ukraine, 2006
342. *Hyssopus angustifolius* M.B.– KF-02, Russia, 2002
343. *Hyssopus officinalis* L. – LR-01
344. *Hyssopus officinalis* L. cv. Atlant– KF-02, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1999
345. *Hyssopus officinalis* L. cv. Markiz– KF-02, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2001
346. *Hyssopus officinalis* L. cv. Vodohrai– KF-02, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2009
347. *Lallemantia iberica* (M.Bieb.) Fisch. & C.A.Mey. – KF-04, Czech Republic, 2003
348. *Lallemantia peltata* (L.) Fisch. & C.A.Mey. – KF-04, Slovakia, 2016
349. *Lavandula angustifolia* Mill.– KF-02, England, 2004; KD-13
350. *Lavandula angustifolia* Mill. f. *bilo-kvitkova*– KF-02, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2008
351. *Marrubium incanum* Desf. – KF-02, Estonia, 2007
352. *Marrubium peregrinum* L. – KF-02, Brno, Czech Republic, 2007
353. *Marrubium vulgare* L.– KF-02, Ukraine, 2007
354. *Melissa officinalis* L.– KF-02, Germany , 1956; LR-01
355. *Micromeria graeca* (L.) Benth. ex Rchb.– KF-02, Netherlands, 2015
356. *Monarda bradburiana* L.– KF-02, Germany , 1986
357. *Monarda didyma* L.– KF-02, Ukraine, 1954
358. *Monarda fistulosa* L.– KF-02, Canada, 2006
359. *Nepeta argolica* Bory et Chaub. (*Nepeta sibthorpii* Benth.) – KF-07, Switzerland, 2007
360. *Nepeta cataria* L. – KF-07, Moskow, Russia, 2006
361. *Nepeta cataria* L. var. *citriodora* Dum. – KF-07, Poland, 2012
362. *Nepeta cataria* L. var. *citriodora* Dum, cv. Melodiia– KF-02, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1999
363. *Nepeta distans* Royle – KF-07, Germany, 2007
364. *Nepeta elliptica* Royle ex Benth.– KF-02, Poland, 2012; KF-07, Вроцлав, Poland, 2006
365. *Nepeta* × *faaseni* Bergmans ex Stearn – KD-13
366. *Nepeta grandiflora* M.Bieb. – KF-07, Germany, 2011
367. *Nepeta italica* L.– KF-02, Hungary, 1964
368. *Nepeta mussinii* Spreng. ex Henckel – KF-07, Italy, 2007
369. *Nepeta mussinii* Spreng. ex Henckel cv. Посвята Мейсу – KF-07, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2016
370. *Nepeta parnassica* Heldr. ex Sart. – KF-07, England, 2007
371. *Nepeta sibirica* L. cv. Чапoіra – KF-07, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2013
372. *Nepeta transcaucasica* Grossh. – KF-07, Ukraine, 2006
373. *Nicotiana alata* Link & Otto – KD-05
374. *Nicotiana longiflora* Cav. – KD-05
375. *Nicotiana* × *sandere hort.* – KD-05
376. *Nicotiana* × *sandere* 'Little Nicry' – KD-05
377. *Nicotiana* × *sandere* 'Red' – KD-05
378. *Nicotiana langsdorffii* Weinmann – KD-05
379. *Nicotiana sylvestris* Speg. & S. Comes – KD-05
380. *Ocimum* × *africanum* Lour. – KF-07, France, 2014
381. *Ocimum basilicum* L.– KF-02, Crimea, Ukraine, 1972
382. *Ocimum basilicum* L. cv. Тонус – KF-07, Kyiv, Ukraine, 2016
383. *Ocimum basilicum* L. var. *cinnammomum*– KF-02, Germany , 2004
384. *Ocimum basilicum* L. var. *citriodorum* – KF-02, Germany , 2004
385. *Ocimum basilicum* L. var. *crispum* E. G. Camus – KF-07, Moldova, 2012
386. *Ocimum basilicum* L. var. *piperita* – KF-07, France, 2014
387. *Ocimum gratissimum* L.– KF-02, Ukraine, 1974

388. *Ocimum tenuiflorum* L. – KF-07, France, 2014; KF-02, Germany , 2004
389. *Origanum vulgare* L. – KF-02, Germany, 1946
390. *Origanum vulgare* L. cv. *Rosea*– KF-02, Czech Republic, 2003
391. *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt.– KF-02, Japan, 2002
392. *Phlomis herba-venti* subsp. *pungens* (Willd.) Maire ex DeFilipps – PF-10
393. *Phlomis tuberosa* L. – PF-08
394. *Phlomoide tuberosa* (L.) Moench – LR-01
395. *Physostegia virginiana* (L.) Benth. – LR-01
396. *Salvia aethiopsis* L. – KF-02, Moldova, 1973
397. *Salvia azurea* Michx. ex Vahl – KF-07, France, 2018
398. *Salvia bucharica* Popov– KF-02, Germany , 2008
399. *Salvia cadmica* Boiss. – KF-07, Germany , 2015
400. *Salvia coccinea* Buc'hoz ex Etl. – KD-05
401. *Salvia coccinea* 'Coral Nipha' – KD-05
402. *Salvia fruticosa* Mill. – KF-07, Belgium, 2017
403. *Salvia glutinosa* L. – PF-09, Ukrainian Carpathians
404. *Salvia hispanica* L. – KF-04, Germany, 2013
405. *Salvia judaica* Boiss. – KF-07, Czech Republic, 2017
406. *Salvia nemorosa* L. – KF-02, Moldova, 1973; LR-01
407. *Salvia nemorosa* L. cv. *Rosakenigin* – KF-02, Germany , 2008
408. *Salvia officinalis* L. – KF-02, Crimea, Ukraine, 2004
409. *Salvia officinalis* subsp. *lavandulifolia* (Vahl) Gams – KF-07, Germany , 2013
410. *Salvia patens* Cav. – KF-02, Brno, Czech Republic, 2001
411. *Salvia scabiosifolia* Lam. – PF-10
412. *Salvia sclarea* L. cv. *Kardynal*– KF-02, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2004
413. *Salvia sclarea* var. *turkestanica* Mottet. – KF-02, KF-02, Italy, 2009
414. *Salvia splendens* Sellow ex Schult. – KD-05
415. *Salvia tomentosa* Mill. – KD-13; PF-10
416. *Salvia verticillata* L. – KF-02, Crimea, Ukraine, 2008
417. *Satureja hortensis* L. – KF-02, Russia, 1976
418. *Satureja montana* L. – KF-02, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1976
419. *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi. – LR-01
420. *Scutellaria zhongdianensis* – KF-07, Germany , 2015
421. *Sideritis montana* L. – KF-07, Germany, 2017
422. *Stachys officinalis* (L.) Trevis. – LR-01
423. *Teucrium chamaedrys* L. – LR-01
424. *Teucrium scorodonia* L. – KF-07, Germany , 2012

LARDIZABALACEAE

425. *Akebia quinata* (Houtt.) Decne. (hybr.) – PR-07

LEGUMINOSAE

426. *Astragalus galegiformis* L. – KF-01, Russia, 1973
427. *Astragalus ponticus* Pall. – KF-01, Kaunas, Lithuania, 1970
428. *Baptisia australis* (L.) R. Br. – KD-13; KF-01, Russia, 1978
429. *Cercis canadensis* L. – DN-04
430. *Cicer arietinum* L. – KF-01, 1993
431. *Colutea arborescens* L. – DN-04
432. *Colutea orientalis* Mill. – DN-04
433. *Desmodium canadense* (L.) DC. – KF-01, Moskow, Russia, 1968
434. *Galega orientalis* Lam. – PF-12
435. *Galega orientalis* Lam. cv. *Kavkazkyi branets*– KF-01, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1996
436. *Genista tinctoria* – KF-04, Germany , 2012
437. *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L. – KF-01, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1988; LR-01
438. *Indigofera heterantha* Brandis – KF-04, London, England, 2011
439. *Lablab purpureus* (L.) Sweet – KF-01, 1993; KD-05
440. *Laburnum alpinum* (Mill.) Berchold et Presl. – DN-04
441. *Laburnum anagyroides* Medik. – DN-04
442. *Laburnum watereri* (Wettst.) Dipp. – DN-04

- 443. *Lathyrus grandiflorus* Sibth. Smith – KF-01, Italy, 2005
- 444. *Lathyrus latifolius* L. – KD-13
- 445. *Lathyrus sylvestris* L. × *L. latifolius* L. cv. Popeliuschka – KF-01, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1998
- 446. *Lupinus mutabilis* Sweet. – KD-05
- 447. *Onobrychis arenaria* (Kit.) D. C. – KF-01, Chabany, Ukraine, 1969
- 448. *Onobrychis grandis* Lip. – KF-01, Moskow, Russia, 1960
- 449. *Phaseolus coccineus* L. – KD-05
- 450. *Spartium junceum* L. – KF-04, Кіль, Germany, 2012
- 451. *Trigonella caerulea* (L.) Ser. – KF-02, Riga, Latvia, 1987
- 452. *Trigonella foenum-graecum* L. – LR-01

LILIACEAE

- 453. *Erythronium caucasicum* Woronow – PF-12
- 454. *Fritillaria grandiflora* Grossh. – PF-12
- 455. *Lilium monadelphum* M.Bieb. – PF-12

LINACEAE

- 456. *Linum austriacum* L. – KF-04, Kyiv, Ukraine, 2004
- 457. *Linum grandiflorum* – KF-04, Kyiv, Ukraine, 2004
- 458. *Linum humile* Mill. L. – KF-05.2, Ukraine, 2005
- 459. *Linum perenne* L. – LR-01
- 460. *Linum usitatissimum* L. – KD-05
- 461. *Linum usitatissimum* 'Alba' – KD-05
- 462. *Linum usitatissimum* 'Fibriferum' – KD-05
- 463. *Linum usitatissimum* 'Natasja' – KD-05
- 464. *Linum usitatissimum* 'Oleiferum' – KD-05
- 465. *Linum usitatissimum* 'Szegedi Olaglen' – KD-05

MAGNOLIACEAE

- 466. *Magnolia* × *loebneri* Kache – DN-10
- 467. *Magnolia kobus* DC. – DN-10
- 468. *Magnolia* × *soulangeana* Soul.-Bod. – DN-10

MALVACEAE

- 469. *Abutilon theophrasti* Medik – KD-05
- 470. *Alcea nudiflora* (Lindl.) Boiss. – PF-13, Kopet Dag, 1961
- 471. *Alcea rugosa* Alef. – PF-08
- 472. *Hibiscus esculentus* L. – KF-03, Turkmenistan, 1961
- 473. *Hibiscus manihot* (L.) Medik. – KF-04, Germany, 2007
- 474. *Lavatera thuringiaca* L. – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 1990; PF-08
- 475. *Lavatera trimestris* L. 'Silver Cup' – KD-05
- 476. *Malva parviflora* L. f. *nyzkorosla* – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2010
- 477. *Malva crispa* L. – KF-01, Russia, 1965
- 478. *Malva crispa* L. × *M. pulchella* Bernh. cv. Nika – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2001
- 479. *Malva crispa* L. cv. Rada – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2003
- 480. *Malva meluca* Graebn. – KF-01, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2009
- 481. *Malva meluca* Graebn. × *M. crispa* L. cv. Unava – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 1999
- 482. *Malva moschata* L. – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2001
- 483. *Malva moschata* L. 'Albiflora' – KD-05
- 484. *Malva sylvestris* L. – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 1987
- 485. *Malva trida* Cav. 'Rosea' – KD-05
- 486. *Malva verticillata* L. cv.s. Ikva – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 1994
- 487. *Sida hermaphrodita* (L.) Rusby. – KF-01, Russia, 1946
- 488. *Sida hermaphrodita* Rusby, cv. Fitoenerhiia – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2008
- 489. *Tilia begoniifolia* Steven – DN-07
- 490. *Tilia dasystyla* Steven – DN-07
- 491. *Tilia mongolica* Maxim. – DN-07
- 492. *Tilia petiolaris* DC. – DN-07
- 493. *Tilia sibirica* Bayer – PF-14, Altai

MELANTHIACEAE

494. *Veratrum nigrum* L. – PF-11

NYCTAGINACEAE

495. *Mirabilis jalapa* L. 'Rosea' – KD-05

OLEACEAE

496. *Fraxinus chinensis* subsp. *rhyrachophylla* (Hance) A.E.Murray – PF-15, Russia, Kedrovaya Pad, 1950
497. *Syringa amurensis* Rupr. – DN-08
498. *Syringa fauriei* Lev. – DN-08
499. *Syringa pekinensis* Rupr. – DN-08
500. *Syringa pubescens* Turcz. – DN-08
501. *Syringa reticulata* subsp. *amurensis* (Rupr.) P.S.Green & M.C.Chang. – PF-15, Russia, 1950
502. *Syringa villosa* subsp. *wolfii* (C.K.Schneid.) Jin Y.Chen & D.Y.Hong – PF-15, Russia

ONAGRACEAE

503. *Clarkia concinna* (Fisch. & C.A.Mey.) Greene – KD-05
504. *Clarkia purpurea* (Curtis) Nels & Macbr. – KD-05
505. *Oenothera biennis* L. – KF-04, Czech Republic, 2002

ORCHIDACEAE

506. *Dactylorhiza majalis* (Rchb.) P.F.Hunt & Summerh. – PF-11
507. *Epipactis palustris* (L.) Crantz – PF-11

PAPAVERACEAE

508. *Argemone munita* Dur. & Hilg. – KD-05
509. *Argemone ochroleuca* Sweet – KD-05
510. *Corydalis caucasica* DC. – PF-12
511. *Dicranostigma franchetianum* – KD-06, Strasbourg, France, 2006
512. *Eschscholzia californica* Cham. – KD-05
513. *Eschscholzia californica* 'Orang' – KD-05
514. *Eschscholzia californica* 'Red Chief' – KD-05
515. *Eschscholzia lobii* Greene – KD-06, Germany, 2004
516. *Glaucium corniculatum* (L.) Curtis – KD-06, Dijon, France, 2016
517. *Glaucium flavum* Crantz – LR-01; KD-06, Orto Botanico Dell'Universita di padova , Italia , 2000
518. *Glaucium squamigerum* Kar. et Kir Techn. – KD-06, Universität Dresden Botanischer Garten, 2001
519. *Hunnemannia fumariifolia* Sweet – KD-06, Germany, 2004
520. *Papaver atlanticum* (Ball) Cosson – KD-06, Giardino Botanico Alpino Rezia, 2003
521. *Papaver glaucum* "Ladybird" Boiss. and Hausskn – KD –06, Swallowtail Garden Seeds, Canada, 2002
522. *Papaver nudicaule* L. – KD-06, Giardino Botanico Alpino Rezia, 2000
523. *Papaver orientale* L. – KD-06, Leipzig, Germany, 2003

PHYLLANTHACEAE

524. *Flueggea suffruticosa* (Pall.) Baill. – PF-15, Russia, Kedrovaya Pad, 1950

PHYTOLACCACEAE

525. *Phytolacca americana* L. – KF-04, Germany , 1999
526. *Phytolacca esculenta* Van Houtte– KF-04, Ukraine, 2011

PINACEAE

527. *Larix sibirica* Ledeb. – PF-14, Altai
528. *Picea asperata* Mast. – DN-01
529. *Pseudotsuga menziesii* (Mirb.) Franco var. *menziesii* – DN-01, Hauber firm, Germany, 1947

PIPERACEAE

530. *Peperomia bicolor* Sodiro – TR-02

- 531. *Peperomia hirta* C. DC – TR-02
- 532. *Peperomia maculosa* (Linné) Hook. – TR-02
- 533. *Peperomia nigropunctata* Miquel – TR-02

PLANTAGINACEAE

- 534. *Antirrhinum majus* 'Sonora' – KD-05
- 535. *Antirrhinum majus* L. – KD-05
- 536. *Chelone glabra* L. – KD-05
- 537. *Digitalis purpurea* L. – LR-01
- 538. *Penstemon digitalis* Nutt. ex Sims 'Purpurea' – KD-13
- 539. *Plantago lanceolata* L. – LR-01
- 540. *Plantago major* L. – LR-01
- 541. *Plantago major* L. cv. *Atropurpurea* – KD-13
- 542. *Veronica spicata* L. 'Alba' – KD-13

POACEAE

- 543. *Agrostis stolonifera* L. cv. *Klonova* – KF-06, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1993
- 544. *Agrostis tenuis* Sibth. cv. *Desnianska 51* – KF-06, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1993
- 545. *Alopecurus pratensis* L. – KF-06, Ukraine, 2012
- 546. *Briza maxima* L. – KD-14
- 547. *Briza media* L. – KD-14
- 548. *Deschampsia cespitosa* (L.) P. Beauv. – KD-14
- 549. *Deschampsia flexuosa* (L.) Trin. – KD-14
- 550. *Echinochloa frumentaceae* Link. – KF-05.3, Ukraine, 2006
- 551. *Eleusine coracana* (L.) Gaertn. cv. *Tropikanka* – KF-01, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2001
- 552. *Festuca cinerea* Vill. – KD-14; KF-06, Germany, 1993
- 553. *Festuca curvula* Gaudid – KF-06, France, 2004
- 554. *Festuca glauca* Vill. – KF-06, Estonia, 2004
- 555. *Festuca heterophylla* Lam. – KF-06, Hungary, 2003
- 556. *Festuca nigrescens* Lat. – KF-06, Hungary, 2004
- 557. *Festuca ovina* L. cv. *Superba* – KF-06, Czech Republic, 2004
- 558. *Festuca ovina* L. cv. *Turnament* – KF-06, Russia, 2004
- 559. *Festuca ovina* L. cv. *Zabava* – KF-06, Ukraine, 2004
- 560. *Festuca pallens* Host – KF-06, Romania, 2004
- 561. *Festuca rubra* L. cv. *Ahata* – KF-06, Ukraine, 2004
- 562. *Festuca rubra* L. cv. *Ahram* – KF-06, Russia, 2004
- 563. *Festuca rubra* L. cv. *Barzhena* – KF-06, Russia, 2004
- 564. *Festuca rubra* L. cv. *Bohdanka* – KF-06, Ukraine, 2010
- 565. *Festuca rubra* L. cv. *Frida* – KF-06, Russia, 2004
- 566. *Festuca rubra* L. cv. *Liproza* – KF-06, Germany, 2010
- 567. *Festuca rubra* L. cv. *Livizion* – KF-06, Germany, 2010
- 568. *Festuca rubra* L. cv. *Syretska* – KF-06, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2004
- 569. *Festuca rubra* L. cv. *Yanka* – KF-06, Ukraine, 2004
- 570. *Festuca rubra* L. cv. *Yasper* – KF-06, Canada, 2010
- 571. *Festuca valesiaca* Gaud. – KF-06, Germany, 2004
- 572. *Hordeum bulbosum* L. – KF-03, Belarus, 1959
- 573. *Hordeum jubatum* L. – KD-14
- 574. *Lamarckia aurea* 'Golden Showers' – KD-14
- 575. *Leymus arenarius* (L.) Hochst. – KD-14
- 576. *Lolium perenne* L. cv. *Andriana-80* – KF-06, Ukraine, 2010
- 577. *Lolium perenne* L. cv. *Lizuna* – KF-06, Germany, 2010
- 578. *Lolium perenne* L. cv. *Osyp* – KF-06, Ukraine, 2012
- 579. *Lolium perenne* L. cv. *Plezir* – KF-06, Germany, 2010
- 580. *Lolium perenne* L. cv. *Sviatoshynskyi* – KF-06, Ukraine, 2010
- 581. *Melica altissima* L. cv. *Alba* – KD-14
- 582. *Melica altissima* L. cv. *Atropurpurea* – KD-14
- 583. *Melica transsilvanica* Schur. – PF-09, Ukrainian Carpathians
- 584. *Miscanthus × giganteus* J.M. Greef & Deuter ex Hodk & Renvoize cv. *Huliver* – KF-05.1, Czech Republic, 2004

585. *Miscanthus sacchariflorus* (Maxim) Hackel. – PF-15, Primorsky Krai, Russia, 1959; KD-14
 586. *Miscanthus sacchariflorus* (Maxim.) Benth. cv. Snihopad – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2008
 587. *Miscanthus sinensis* Anderss. cv. Veleten – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2004
 588. *Panicum virgatum* L. – KD-14
 589. *Panicum virgatum* L. cv. Zoriane – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2010
 590. *Pennisetum alopecuroides* (L.) Spreng. – KD-14
 591. *Poa pratensis* L. cv. Kompakt – KF-06, Denmark, 2010
 592. *Sesleria caerulea* (L.) Ard. – KD-14
 593. *Setaria italica* (L.) Beauv. ssp. maxima (Alef.) Mansf. – KF-05.3, Ukraine, 2005
 594. *Sorghum alnum* Parodi cv. Kolumbo – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2008
 595. *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench, – KF-05.3, Czech Republic, 2004; KD-14
 596. *Sorghum caffrorum* (Thunb) P. Beauw – KF-05.3, Czech Republic, 2012
 597. *Sorghum dochna* (Forsk.) Snowd. – KF-05.3, Czech Republic, 2011
 598. *Sorghum durra* (Forsk.) Stapf – KF-05.3, France, 2012
 599. *Sorghum nigricans* (Puiz et Pav.) Snow. – KF-05.3, Germany, 2012
 600. *Sorghum nigrum* Roemer & Schultes – KF-05.3, Ukraine, 2007
 601. *Sorghum saccharatum* (L.) Moench. – KF-05.3, Ukraine, 2007; KF-04, France, 1995
 602. *Sorghum saccharatum* (L.) Moench, cv. Botanichniyi – KF-05.3, Ukraine, 2010
 603. *Sorghum sudanense* (Piper)Stapt. – KF-05.3, Ukraine, 2009
 604. *Sorghum technicum* (Koern.) Bait.et Trab. – KF-05.3, Ukraine, 2007
 605. *Sorghum vulgare* Pers. – KF-05.3, Ukraine, 2007
 606. *Stipa calamagrostis* cv. 'Lempert' – KD-14
 607. *Stipa capillata* L. – PF-08
 608. *Stipa pulcherrima* K.Koch. – KD-14
 609. *Stipa tenacissima* L. – KF-04, Люблін, Poland, 2011
 610. *Stipa ucrainica* P.Smirn – KD-14

POLEMONIACEAE

611. *Collomia grandiflora* Douglas ex Lindl. – KF-07, France, 2015
 612. *Gilia achilleifolia* Bent. 'Coerulea' – KD-05
 613. *Phlox drummondii* Hook. 'Beauty White' – KD-05

POLYGONACEAE

614. *Polygonum panjutinii* Kharkev. – PF-12
 615. *Rhenum rhaponticum* L.– KF-03, Russia, 1959
 616. *Rumex acetosa* L.– KF-03, Switzerland, 2002
 617. *Rumex confertus* Wild – PF-08
 618. *Rumex japonicus* L. – KF-01, Moskow, Russia, 1977
 619. *Rumex patientia* L. – KF-01, Russia, 1961
 620. *Rumex tianschanicus* Losinsk. – PF-13, Trans-Ili Alatau, Kazakhstan, 1961; KF-01, Republic of Mordovia, Russia
 621. *Rumex tuberosus* L. – KF-01, Germany, 1984
 622. *Shchavnat* (*Rumex patientia* L. × *R. tianschanicus* Losinsk.), cv. Biekor-1 – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2006
 623. *Shchavnat* (*Rumex patientia* L. × *R. tianschanicus* Losinsk.), cv. Nastavnyk – KF-05.1, Ukraine, 2008

PORTULACACEAE

624. *Portulaca grandiflora* Hook. – KD-05
 625. *Portulaca oleracea* L.– KF-03, Moldova, 1959

PRIMULACEAE

626. *Lysimachia punktata* L. – KD-13
 627. *Primula denticulata* Sm. – KD-13
 628. *Primula denticulata* Sm. 'Alba' – KD-13
 629. *Primula saxatilis* Kom. – KD-13

RANUNCULACEAE

630. *Aconitum kusnezoffii* Rechb. – KD-13
 631. *Anemone canadensis* L. – KD-13

- 632. *Anemone rivularis* Buch.-Ham. Ex DC. var. *flore-minore* Maxim – KD-13
- 633. *Aquilegia canadensis* L. – KD-13
- 634. *Aquilegia chrysantha* A.Gray – KD-13
- 635. *Aquilegia vulgaris* L. – LR-01
- 636. *Clematis brevicaudata* DC – PF-15, Primorsky Krai, Russia, 1953
- 637. *Clematis terniflora* var. *manshurica* (Rupr.) Ohwi – PF-15, Vladivostok, Russia, 1957
- 638. *Consolida ajacis* (L.) Schur – KD-05
- 639. *Helleborus caucasicus* A. Braun – KD-13
- 640. *Helleborus purpurascens* Waldst. & Kit – KD-13; PF-11
- 641. *Nigella arvensis* L. – KF-02, Germany, 2002
- 642. *Nigella bucharica* Schipcz. – KD-05
- 643. *Nigella ciliaris* DC. – KF-02, Germany, 2001
- 644. *Nigella damascena* L.– KF-02, England, 1999
- 645. *Nigella sativa* L. – KF-05.2, Ukraine, 2009
- 646. *Nigella sativa* L. cv. *Diana* – KF-02, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2004
- 647. *Pulsatilla vulgaris* Mill.'Dissecta' – KD-13
- 648. *Thalictrum flavum* L. – LR-01
- 649. *Thalictrum minus* L. – KD-13

RHAMNACEAE

- 650. *Zizyphus jujuba* Mill. – PR-07

ROSACEAE

- 651. *Agrimonia eupatoria* L.– KF-04, Poland, 2009
- 652. *Aruncus vulgaris* (Maxim.) Raf. ex H.Hara – PF-09, Ukrainian Carpathians
- 653. *Cerasus tomentosa* (Thunb.) Wall. ex T.T. Yu & C.L. Li – PF-15, Primorsky Krai, Russia, 1953
- 654. *Chaenomeles japonica* (Thunb.) Lindl. – PR-07
- 655. *Crataegus dsungarica* Zabel ex Lange – PF-13, Trans-Ili Alatau, Kazakhstan, 1961
- 656. *Crataegus monogyna* Jacq. – PF-09, Ukrainian Carpathians
- 657. *Crataegus pinnatifida* Bunge – PF-15
- 658. *Cydonia oblonga* Mill. – PR-07
- 659. *Cydonia oblonga* Mill. cv. *Akademicheskaja* – PR-07
- 660. *Cydonia oblonga* Mill. cv. *Darunok onuku* – PR-07
- 661. *Cydonia oblonga* Mill. cv. *Grushevidnaia Shaidarovoy* – PR-07
- 662. *Cydonia oblonga* Mill. cv. *Grushevidnaia Shumskogo* – PR-07
- 663. *Cydonia oblonga* Mill. cv. *Kievskaja aromatnaia* – PR-07
- 664. *Cydonia oblonga* Mill. cv. *Mariya* – PR-07
- 665. *Cydonia oblonga* Mill. cv. № 8 *Kaschenko* – PR-07
- 666. *Cydonia oblonga* Mill. cv. № 18 *Kaschenko* – PR-07
- 667. *Cydonia oblonga* Mill. cv. *Oranzhevaia* – PR-07
- 668. *Cydonia oblonga* Mill. cv. *Shkolnitsa* – PR-07
- 669. *Cydonia oblonga* Mill. cv. *Studentka* – PR-07
- 670. *Geum coccineum* Sibth. & Sm. – KD-13
- 671. *Geum rivale* L. – KD-13
- 672. *Geum urbanum* L.– KF-02, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 1976
- 673. *Malus Niedzwetzkyana* Dieck. – PR-07
- 674. *Malus pumila* Mill. 'Elise Rathke' – PR-07
- 675. *Malus pumila* Mill. 'Luiza' – PR-07
- 676. *Mespilus germanica* L. – PR-07
- 677. *Potentilla recta* L. – KD-13
- 678. *Poterium polygamum* L. – KF-01, Kherson, Ukraine, 1974
- 679. *Pyrus ussuriensis* Maxim. ex Rupr. – PF-15
- 680. *Rosa canina* L. – PF-01, PF-08
- 681. *Rosa pendulina* L. – PF-09, Ukrainian Carpathians
- 682. *Rubus idaeus* L. – PF-14
- 683. *Rubus montanus* Lib. ex Lej. – PF-09, Ukrainian Carpathians
- 684. *Sanguisorba minor* Scop.– LR-01
- 685. *Sanguisorba officinalis* L. – LR-01
- 686. *Sorbus alnifolia* (Siebold & Zucc.) K.Koch – PF-15

687. *Sorbus domestica* L. – PR-07
688. *Sorbus sibirica* Hedl. – PF-14, Altai
689. *Sorbus torminalis* (L.) Crantz. – PF-01

RUBIACEAE

690. *Rubia tinctorum* L. – LR-01; PF-13, Kazakhstan, 1962; KF-04, Beresototscha, Ukraine

RUTACEAE

691. *Phellodendron amurense* Rupr. – PF-15, Russia, Kedrovaya Pad, 1950
692. *Ruta corsica* DC. – KF-07, France, 2016
693. *Ruta graveolens* L. – KF-02, Germany, 1997; KD-13
694. *Tetradium daniellii* (Benn.) T.G.Hartley – DN-10

SAPINDACEAE

695. *Acer campestre* L. – PF-01
696. *Acer griseum* (Franch.) Pax – DN-07
697. *Acer heldreichii* subsp. *trautvetteri* (Medw.) A.E.Murray – DN-07
698. *Acer mandshuricum* Maxim – PF-15, Russia, Kedrovaya Pad, 1952
699. *Acer nikoense* (Miq.) Maxim. – DN-07
700. *Acer opalus* Mill. – DN-07
701. *Acer pictum* Thunb. – PF-15, Primorsky Krai, Russia, 1950
702. *Acer platanoides* L. – PF-01
703. *Acer tataricum* subsp. *ginnala* (Maxim.) Wesm. – DN-07
704. *Acer velutinum* Boiss. – DN-07
705. *Cardiospermum halicacabum* L. – KD-05
706. *Koelreuteria paniculata* Laxm. – DN-07

SCHIZANDRACEAE

707. *Schizandra chinensis* (Turcz.) Baill. – PR-11

SCROPHULARIACEAE

708. *Chaenorhinum minus* (L.) Lange – KD-05

STAPHYLEACEAE

709. *Staphylea colchica* Stev. – DN-04
710. *Staphylea trifolia* L. – DN-04

SOLANACEAE

711. *Datura stramonium* L. – KF-04, Germany, 2013; LR-01
712. *Lycium barbarum* L. – PR-07
713. *Lycium chinense* Mill. – PR-07
714. *Nicandra physalodes* (L.) Gaertn – KF-01, Russia, 1976; KF-05.2, Ukraine, 2005
715. *Petunia integrifolia* (Hook.) Schinz & Thell. – KD-05
716. *Petunia x hybrida* hort. – KD-05
717. *Petunia x hybrida* 'Fantazy mix' – KD-05
718. *Petunia x hybrida* 'Rosy of Heven' – KD-05
719. *Physalis ixocarpa* Brot. ex. Hornem cv. *Likhtaryk* – KF-03, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2003
720. *Physalis peruviana* L. – KF-03, Germany, 2000
721. *Physalis pubescens* L. cv. *Zharynka* – KF-03, Kyiv (NBG), Ukraine, 2003
722. *Scopolia carniolica* Jacq. – PF-09, Ukrainian Carpathians; PF-12
723. *Solanum dulcamara* L. – LR-01
724. *Schizanthus pinnatus* Ruiz & Pav. – KD-05
725. *Schizanthus x wisetonensis* hort. – KD-05

TALINACEAE

726. *Talinum paniculatum* (Jacq.) Gaertn. – KD-05

TAXACEAE

727. *Taxus baccata* L. – PF-11; DN-02, Lviv, 1964

728. *Taxus cuspidata* Sieb. et Zucc. – DN-01, Far East, 1955; PF-15, Hualaza, Russia, 1951

THYMELAEACEAE

729. *Daphne mezereum* L. – PF-11

URTICACEAE

730. *Urtica cannabina* L. – KF-01, Omsk, Russia, PF-14

731. *Urtica pilulifera* L. – KF-04, Germany, 2016

VERBENACEAE

732. *Glandularia canadensis* (L.) Small – KD-05

733. *Vitex agnus-castus* L. – KF-02, Germany, 1989

734. *Vitex negundo* L. – KF-02, Crimea, Ukraine, 1993

735. *Vitex negundo* var. *cannabifolia* L. cv. Komandor – KF-02, Kyiv (NKG), Ukraine, 2017

VITACEAE

736. *Vitis amurensis* Rupr. – PF-15, Russia, 1950

XANTHORRHOEACEAE

737. *Asphodeline lutea* (L.) Rchb. – PF-10; PF-11

738. *Asphodeline taurica* (Pall.) Endl. – PF-10

Plant nomenclature is mainly based on:

***The Plant List* (2013). Version 1.1. Published on the Internet; <http://www.theplantlist.org/>**

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